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Analyzing the Factors Influencing the Adoption and Acceptance of Mobile Banking

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, banking and financial sector have shown tremendous progress. The transition from traditional banking to electronic banking added considerable value to customers and banking institutions. It is generally perceived that the adoption of mobile banking is low and below average in several rural area of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province of Pakistan. Therefore, it was chosen to carry out the research and examine the factors affecting the adoption of mobile banking in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province of Pakistan. The targeted survey population of this research work was the current customers of mobile based banking of KP. The survey questionnaire was developed using Google Forms and widespread via email, social media sites, and directly to different contacts via SMS and WhatsApp. The same questionnaire was also distributed in printed hard copy form to a limited locality. Further to find out the association and impact of different variables the descriptive frequency, correlation, regression, and cross tabulation analysis were conducted. A significant positive correlation observed among predictor (independent) and predicted (dependent) variables. The outcomes of regression assessment revealed that ease of use (EOU), social influence (SOI) and System quality (SYQ) have positive and statistically noteworthy impression on adoption of mobile banking in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan. These findings suggest that Khyber Pakhtunkhwa needs a more user-friendly mobile banking system, greater social influence, and a high-quality system to boost digital transformation and financial inclusion.

Keywords: Mobile banking Adoption, Social Influence, System Quality, Ease of Use, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bank is defined as an established financial institution formally authorized by the government. A bank can work in variety of ways and offer different financial services e.g., accept deposits, give loans, and process the cheques for his/her customers. Mainly, the role of a bank against the financial transactions is intermediary. For many decades banking services were limited to rich and wealthy people. Nowadays the banking activities are expended from personal banking to investment and corporate banking (Lin, 2011). A bank account has become as a basic requirement to work around and participate in day to day financial activities. With the passage of time banking sector incorporated other types of activities like foreign exchange trading, insurance, and trading in equities (Gupta, 2013). Similarly, the channels and medium of banking services are also advanced. The branch oriented and in-person banking had been popular for many decades but now the technological advancement enabled the banks to automate the processes of banking services e.g., automated teller machines (ATM) eliminated the requirements of cheques for cash withdrawals or funds transfer (Khraim et al., 2011).

During the last few years, the telecommunication sector has shown major improvement and enabled the people living in developed and even in under develop countries to have access to high speed telecommunication and Internet services (Hibberd, 2007). This advancement has enabled many businesses to grow exponentially and reached millions of customers (Zhang et al., 2018). With this shift of paradigm, the banking services are also shifted from traditional to online-banking and mobile based banking (Shaikh & Karjaluo, 2015). As per publications of "Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA)", mobile phone/cell subscribers have reached more than 161 million by July 2019, about 70 million subscribers are using 3G/4G services. The broadband subscribers are also increasing and reach about 72 million mark by July 2019 (PTA, 2019). The electronic banking institutions have progressed in the mobile based banking facilities and structure for providing the services to low income population. By 2013, about 115 billion (US\$) had been spent on infrastructure and implementation of mobile and online banking (Alalwan et al., 2017). In Pakistan, popular mobile banking services are identified as EasyPaisa (Telenor) , uPaisa (Ufone), Omni (UBL) , JazzCash (Mobilink), Zong PayMax (Zong) , Keenu Wallet (Keenu) and SimSim (Finja). Besides these mobile banking services, nowadays almost every bank is providing mobile based software and banking application to access and execute the banking services over the smart handheld devices running Android (Google Inc.) or iOS (Apple) operating systems. The most common applications or services of mobile banking are bill payments, mobile load, money transfer, insurance, savings, financing, donations, campaigns, retail purchase, international remittance, insurance, cashback offers, buy vouchers, scan & pay using QR codes, account management, ATM card etc. (Rehan, 2017).

Reference to mobile banking services, few studies had been conducted and focused on acceptance of mobile based banking in developed countries. However, it is evidence from existing updated literature that the relationship between predictors of mobile based banking adoption is still a grey area particularly in the context of rural areas of developing countries such as Pakistan. In Pakistan, mobile banking acceptance and usage is considerably low especially in less develop areas. Few studies & researches have been performed to identify the adoption/usage of mobile based banking but none of them focused on Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province. Therefore, the main and foremost objective of this research study is filling the research gap via examining the factors affecting the satisfaction as well as loyalty of available mobile banking in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Online Banking

Online banking is digital and most convenient form of banking. The banking services are available 24/7 online. The online banking services permit the customers to see and download the account statements, can transfer money, pay bills technically from anywhere any time over the telecommunication or Internet services. The highly common forms of online banking are Internet and mobile based banking (Zhang et al., 2018). The Internet based banking facilitates the customers to carry out financial queries and transactions over the Internet by accessing the banking website or web portal of the bank. This involves the use of computers or laptops connected with Internet service provided by Internet Service Provider (ISP)(Tam & Oliveira, 2017). Similarly, the mobile banking refers to a more advanced form of banking services where the customer can remotely conduct the banking transactions over the handheld devices like smartphone and tablets. The mobile based banking is offered via SMS, Mobile world wide web, or smart mobile application (Okazaki, 2005). The mobile user can access and use the banking financial services 24/7 from everywhere and anytime. With the advancement telecommunication systems and innovation of banking services a new type of banking has emerged called branchless or direct banking. Such banks do not require local branches or face-to-face appearance and interaction with customers e.g., EasyPaisa, Omni etc. The advancement of information & communication technology (ICT) has a massive effect on development of convenient and friendly banking. The integration of telecommunication systems and financial services has created new platform for rapid development of mobile banking systems. Mobile banking systems give freedom, convenience, and economical way of banking. Mobile banking brought projection for the banks to reach a large banking market through mobile services (Lee et al., 2007). Mobile phones, tablets, and other handheld devices are being extensively used everywhere, this banking evolution has enabled the banking industry to reach the people who still haven't access to banking services (CGAP, 2006). Mobile banking is considered more sophisticated form of electronic banking and possessed more unique and advanced features of information, services, and system quality (Tam and Oliveira 2017). The mobile based banking is being observed as breakthrough technology and has substantial impact on overall efficiency of banking services and quality of life of people but motivation to adopt mobile banking system and maintaining loyalty with the mobile banking systems is very low (Siyal et al., 2019). General availability and mobility of mobile and telecom service is very important. The mobile users want 24/7 round the clock banking services along with the leverage of mobility (Raza et al., 2017).

In Pakistan, mobile phone usage is increasing day by day. Reference to reports published by "State Bank of Pakistan" (SBP, 2019) Branch-less banking is significantly getting importance among other banking channels. The branchless banking accounts reached 51 Million in first quarter of 2019 with having 3 Million transaction per day (see, Table 1).

Table 1: Key Indicators - Branchless Banking (SBP, 2019)

Period	Quarter	No. of Agents	No. of Accounts	Average No. of Transaction per day
2018	Q1	403100	38507887	2398849
	Q2	405571	39246468	2051068
	Q3	413177	43102952	2508365
	Q4	425199	47164779	2966439
2019	Q1	408980	51809393	3288996

Since the availability of different categories of mobile based banking systems in Pakistan, the subscribers are growing and increasing and the number of mobile based banking transactions are also increasing (SBP, 2019) (see, Table 2).

Table 11: Mobile Banking Transaction (SBP, 2019)

S.No.	Product	Items	FY19-Q1	FY19-Q2	FY19-Q3
1	Payment through Mobile Banking	Number of Transactions (Thousands)	312	430	733
		Amount (Million Rupees)	5412	6673	45041
2	Utility Bills Payment through Mobile Banking	Number of Transactions (Thousands)	3467	3904	5272
		Amount (Million Rupees)	5005	4261	4693
3	Intra-Bank Funds Transfer through Mobile Banking	Number of Transactions (Thousands)	1875	2275	3191
		Amount (Million Rupees)	59756	71964	110294
4	Inter-Bank Funds Transfer (IBFT) through Mobile Banking	Number of Transactions (Thousands)	1593	1931	2684
		Amount (Million Rupees)	64831	76953	111275
Total		Number of Transactions (Thousands)	7247	8540	11879
		Amount (Million Rupees)	135005	159851	271303

2.2. Technology Acceptance Models

Acceptance of emerging technologies is most important challenge in banking sector. Several concepts, techniques, and methods are designed to understand the key elements for the adoption of financial systems and technologies.

2.2.1. Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

TRA explain and relate the human behavior on the basis of the customer's intention to accept and show certain conduct (Fishbein et al., 1975). This theory got significant importance and used later by many behavioral and acceptance theories (see, Figure 1).

Figure 11: Framework of TRA

Source: Adapted from the scholarly work of Fishbein et al. (1975).

The theory suggested that the "Behavioral Intention" to accomplish some act is ascertained by the "Attitude Towards Behavior" and other "Subjective Norms". While the ATB is derived from "Behavioral Beliefs" and "Outcomes Evaluation". On the other side the SN are reliant on the "Normative Belief" and another variable of "Motivation to Comply". The theory is mostly utilized to predict and forecast the expected behavior of an individual in certain circumstances.

2.2.2. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM was originally proposed and anticipated by Davis in 1986. TAM is an extension of the TRA model. (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975) (see, Figure 2).

Figure 1: TAM Framework

Source: Adapted from the scholarly work of Davis (1989).

The technology adoption & acceptance is a big challenge of all times. Any new technology introduced faces lots of acceptance, social, quality, security risk, and trust challenges. TAM introduced two new technological adoption features i.e., “Perceived Usefulness (PU)” and “Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)”. Numerous studies have adopted TAM. The studies have proved the significance of this model for examining the technology acceptance in last few years. In a study by Davis (1989) PU and PEOU had been found significant for acceptance of new and emerging technology at the workplace. TAM was also used by Daud et al., (2011) the study and research work found that PU and PEOU influenced the acceptance of m-banking services in Malaysia. Similarly, in another study (Keun et al., 2013), the m-banking adoption is examined by combining the TAM model along with Perceived-Credibility (PC), Perceived-Self-Efficacy (PSE). The researchers also found that PU and PEOU are more significant than PC and PSE to examine the implementation and acceptance of mobile based banking. This model found to be used extensively but had been criticized too for its limitation to incorporate other important variables (Banbasat and Barki, 2007). Similarly, Carter and Belanger (2004) suggested the integration and incorporation of TAM with other models to have more significant understanding of variables.

2.3. Hypotheses Development

2.3.1. Ease of Use (EOU)

Reference to TAM, the predictor variable PEOU is one the major factors. The EOU refers to the extent to which a user considers that using a specific system very easy and free of extensive effort and struggle (Davis, 1989; Liu et al., 2010). Earlier research indicated that perceived-EOU had a major effect and consequence on user’s intention. Regarding mobile based banking, a positive impact had been found by examining PEOU against adoption and loyalty by Luarn and Lin (2005). PEOU has been found has a major attribute in electronic commerce and banking. Cheah et al., (2011) also showed positive connection between PEOU and customer’s behavior & intention for acceptance and usage of mobile based banking in the Malaysia. Another research work done in Kenya, on the factors shaping the intention of users to adopt the mobile based banking showed that EOU was the major factor in usage intention (Lule et al., 2012). A research work done on the acceptance of mobile based banking in the Zimbabwe (Chitungo and Munongo, 2013), showed perceived EOU had major effect on customers and thus influenced to use mobile based banking. PEOU describes the required efforts to use the mobile banking novel technology (Raza et al., 2017). Many other studies, like (Liebana-Cabanillas et al, 2017) for mobile banking systems, (Al-Somali et al, 2009) for online banking, (C. Kim et al., 2010) for mobile payments, and (Ko et al., 2009) for mobile shopping found the PEOU as a highly impacting factor for acceptance and usage of mobile based banking. Another study conducted by Makanyeza (2017) concluded that a user-friendly and easy user interface (UI) further encourages the customers to adopt and accept the novel technologies like mobile oriented banking. While the ease of use is also focused by the banking institutions during the developing of mobile and online banking system. It is certainly proved that PEOU has very significant and positive relation for adoption of technology, many studies concluded that to meet the use expectation and to influence the user behavior for adoption the technology and system ought to be useful and easy for users. (Safeena et al., 2012; Shaikh and Karjaluo, 2015; Koksai, 2016; Raza et al., 2017). Consequently, the study’s first research hypothesis is as follows:

H1 Ease of Use (EOU) has a positive impact over use (USE) of mobile based banking services in KP.

2.3.2. Social Influence (SOI)

The influence of community is defined and explained as a level to which an individual or a person identifies that indispensable others recommendation and believe they should adopt and use the novel technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Another researcher Jahya, (2004) found that customers might shift to a socially accepted technology from a non-socially accepted technology. The choice of person to admit the banking services were liable by associates and family (Singh et al, 2010). A survey on 681 Singaporean consumers (Karjaluo et al., 2010), concluded that risks, community standards, and perceived usefulness were mainly the three critical aspects affecting the acceptance of mobile based banking. (Amin et. al., 2007) investigated 158 consumers from a bank in Malaysia concluded that plan to use mobile based banking was greatly influenced by close community. (Yu, 2012) conducted an empirical research in Taiwan, the sample size of about 441 respondents showed community influence as the most important predictor. According to (Rana, Dwivedi, and Williams, 2015); Alsheikh and Bojei, 2014) the perception about a technology tend to change by the values and preferences in the society including friends, family, neighbors, and relatives. Similarly, any shift in adoption of one technology to

another technology by peers also influence the acceptance by others (Baptista et al., 2015; and Dwivedi et al., 2017). The social relationships also influence the acceptance or diversion of customers towards a novel technology (Al-Somali et al., 2009; Williams, et al., 2015). Similarly, Al-Husein and Sadi, (2015) found that social influence (SOI) have positive bearing on the acceptance and usage of mobile based banking in Saudi Arabia. The study's second research hypothesis is as follows:

H2 Social Influence (SOI) certainly develops the use (USE) of mobile based banking services in KP.

2.3.3. System Quality (SYQ)

System quality implies to the effectiveness, efficiency, and precision of the technical service or system. More the system is technically accurate and efficient more is the quality (Shannon & Weaver, 1998). Delone and McLean (2003) considered the Information Systems (IS) success model to effectively evaluate the linkage between system quality & system technology. They defined the system quality as the technical successfulness. System quality can be assessed by examining the response time, reliability, availability and adaptability of the technical system. While (Laforet & Li, 2005) say that it is not necessary that might ensure availability but not guarantee the reliability. Therefore, quality of underline system has neither certain nor perfect conditions, it concentrates on the technological level of a specified system or service relatively (Lee and Chung, 2009). A study by Zhou (2011) highlighted, customers will tend to use and accept the mobile based banking technology more and more only if they are satisfied with the sensitive system quality. Technically accurate and efficient systems impact the motivational level of customers to use and adopt the systems (Peters et al., 2016; Upadhyay & Jahanyan, 2016). Thus, it can be determined that system quality can be measured as an independent variable. Hence the third hypothesis is as follows:

H3 System quality influences the intention of use of mobile banking in KPK province.

Figure 3 shows the theoretical framework of the study for ready reference.

Figure 3: Theoretical Framework

Source: Author's Illustration.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Population and Sampling

In this study the population was not known so probability-based sampling method or technique was not applicable. Therefore, the study focused on non-probability sampling, we cannot employ convenience non-probability sampling that it is also under criticism due to its generalization. Hence snowball sampling was found to be more appropriate technique considering the nature of respondents and to ensure that we have enough responses to justify the requirements of multivariate technique. Hence, for this study we have used an online tool called "Google Forms" to create and distribute the questionnaire online. The questionnaire was mainly distributed online over social media site (i.e., facebook.com) to reach the maximum number of respondents. The same questionnaire has been shared to different contacts to fill and further share the questionnaire to people residing in KP by using the snowball sampling technique. About 171 responses received. The responses were collected in "Google Sheets" and later converted into "Microsoft Excel" file. The data was analyzed through SPSS software for descriptive, correlation, and regression analysis. "Cronbach-Alpha" (α) was used to analyze the reliability of the instrument.

3.2. Measurement Scale

3.2.1. Ease of Use (EOU)

EOU of mobile based banking service was measured with five questionnaire items designed from (Baabdullah et al., 2019; Chong et al., 2012; Davis, 1989; Kim et al., 2009; Luarn & Lin, 2005; and Faqih & Jaradat, 2015). The main focus these questions were on easiness to register and use the mobile based banking service. For the measurement we used "Likert-scale" method of five points with options for response from 1 appearing "Strongly Disagree" to 5 depicting "Strongly Agree".

3.2.2. Social Influence (SOI)

SOI of mobile based banking service was measured with five items adapted mentioned by (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Zhou et al., 2010; Baabdullah et al., 2019). The focus of SOI questions were to recognize if the acceptance and use of the mobile based banking service is correlated to SOI. For the measurement we used "Likert-scale" method of five points with options for response from 1 appearing "Strongly Disagree" to 5 depicting "Strongly Agree".

3.2.3. System Quality (SYQ)

SYQ of mobile banking service was computed with five questionnaire items tailored from (Kim et al., 2004; Zhou, 2011; Baabdullah et al., 2019). The focus of the questions was to calculate and assess the system quality of the mobile based financial services from the customer's perspective. For the measurement we used "Likert-scale" method of five points with options for response from 1 appearing "Strongly Disagree" to 5 depicting "Strongly Agree".

3.2.4. Use of Mobile Banking (USE)

Use of mobile based banking service was computed with seven items from (Curran & Meuter, 2007; Zhou et al., 2010; Martins et al, 2014; Rehan, 2017; Baabdullah et al, 2019). The focus of questions presented in this section was to characterize the usage of different services of mobile based banking systems. For the measurement we have used five-points Likert-scale frequency method with response options from 1 (i.e., "Never") to 5 (i.e., "Very frequently").

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

In reference to the mobile banking customers and respondents of the questionnaire, Table 3 uncovers the demographic particulars of mobile based banking customers in KP, Pakistan. It reveals that 150 (87.7 %) male and 21 (12.3 %) female respondents completed the questionnaire. The total respondents were 171. Similarly, about 82(48.0%) respondent were single while 89(52.0%) respondents were married. It shows a good balance of both single and married respondents of the questionnaire (see, Table 3).

Table 3: Demographic Survey

Factors	Item	Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	150	87.7
	Female	21	12.3
M. S.	Single	82	48.0
	Married	89	52.0
Age	Under 20	1	.6
	21-30	79	46.2
	31-40	69	40.4
	41-50	19	11.1
	51-60	3	1.8
	Above 60	00	0.0
Education	Below SSC	0	0.0
	SSC	0	0.0
	HSSC	3	1.8
	Associate Bachelor	8	4.7
	Bachelor	64	37.4
	Masters	76	44.4
Income	Doctorate	20	11.7
	Less than 25000	41	24.0
	25000-49999	59	34.5
	50000-74999	14	8.2
	75000-99999	28	16.4
Location	100000 or more	29	17.0
	Bannu	6	3.5
	Dera Ismail Khan	3	1.8
	Hazara	122	71.3
	Kohat	6	3.5
Malakand	12	7.0	

Factors	Item	Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
	Mardan	7	4.1
	Peshawar	15	8.8
	Other	00	0.0
Total sample size n = 171			

The results show that, maximum number of responders belongs to age group of 21-30 (46.2%) and 31-40 (40.4%). While from the educational perspective, a majority of respondents are having Bachelors (37.4%) or Masters (44.4%) degree. Interestingly, all income groups are found using mobile banking services. While the income group of 25000-49999 found about 34.5% of all respondents. The Location data shows that most of the respondents of this questionnaire belongs to Hazara Division of KP. The main reason of this was the direct access including printed hardcopy questionnaire submission.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The computed results of correlation investigation are reported in Table 4, The correlation matrix is used to examine the association among the all the variables presented under this research study. The independent or predictor variables EOU ($r = .299$), SYQ ($r = .400$), and SOI ($r = .466$) has strong and positive correlation with the adoption of mobile based banking services (see, Table 4).

Table 1: Correlation Matrix

Variables	EOU	SOI	SYQ	USE
EOU	1			
SOI	.381**	1		
SEQ	.553**	.407**	.656**	
USE	.299**	.496**	.400**	1

4.3. Hypotheses Testing

In order to analyze the conceptual framework, we tested proposed hypothesis as revealed in Table 5.

Table 5: Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesized Path	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Adjusted R Square	F	Significance	
H1	EOU --> USE	.299	4.076	.084	16.610	YES
H2	SOI --> USE	.496	7.422	.241	55.079	YES
H3	SYQ --> USE	.400	5.682	.155	32.283	YES

The first hypothesis of the study hypothesizes positive relation between EOU and USE. The table 5 demonstrate that EOU has a positive impact over USE ($\beta = .299$, $t = 4.076$). Therefore, H1 is accepted. The F value 16.610 shows the overall fitness of the model. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.084 suggests that EOU is responsible for 8.4% for variance in use of mobile based banking. The hypothesis H2 of the study hypothesizes positive relation between SOI and USE. The table 5 demonstrate that SOI certainly develops the USE ($\beta = .496$, $t = 7.422$). Therefore, the H2 is accepted. The F value 55.079 shows the overall fitness of the model. The adjusted R^2 value of .241 suggest that SOI is responsible for 24.1% for variance in use of mobile based banking. The hypothesis H3 of the study hypothesizes positive relation between SYQ and USE. The table 5 demonstrates that SYQ has encouraging consequence against USE ($\beta = .400$, $t = 5.682$). Therefore, the H3 is accepted. The F value 32.283 shows the overall fitness of the model. The adjusted R^2 value of .155 suggest that system quality is responsible for 15.5% for variance in usage of mobile based banking.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Mobile based banking in Pakistan is certainly challenging. Customers want easy, approachable, trustworthy, and quality banking services while banks are working to attain technological advancements and advantages. There are very limited studies available that studied the usage & adoption of mobile based banking services in Pakistan. As per best of our knowledge, even not a single study was conducted in KP province to examine the determinants of mobile based banking. Similarly, the impact of different independent variable over the satisfaction and loyalty is novel of its kind in Pakistan.

Reference to results presented in former sections, the predictor variable ease of use (EOU) has positive impact on usage (USE). The same has been proved by earlier studies that nowadays customers do not visit the banks physically and prefer to use mobile banking channels (Brown et al. 2003; Calisir et al., 2008; Sripalawat et al., 2011; Alalwan et al., 2017; and Dwivedi et al., 2017). In this study a well-accepted correlation and relationship is found among the EOU and adoption of mobile banking. The same has been proved by several earlier studies like Laukkanen (2012), Davies (1989), Cruz et al. (2010), Cheah et al., (2011), Luarn & Lin (2005), Lule et al., (2012). Chitungo and Munongo, (2013), and Liebana-Cabanillas et al., (2017). Similarly, the results of the study are also supported by Safeena et al., (2012), Koksai, (2016), Shaikh and Karjaluo, (2015) and Raza et al., (2017) that ease of use (EOU) is important to qualify over the user expectations and influence on the customer intention and behavior to accept and adopt the mobile banking.

The examination of social influence (SOI) as a determinant of acceptance or usage (USE) of mobile banking is found positive in our results. It means influence of community against the use of mobile based banking technology is verified as presented by earlier studies by Jahya, (2004), Singh et al., (2010), Karjaluo et al., (2010), Amin et al., (2007), Al-Somali et al., (2009) Williams, et al., (2015), Baptista et al., (2015), Dwivedi et al., (2017), and Al-Husein & Sadi, (2015). The results found of social influence (SOI) are also supported by other studies of UTAUT by Yu, (2012) and Zhou et al., (2010). Moreover, the results and finding of this study shows that the system quality (SYQ) has positive relationship with usage (USE) that witnessed to increase the customer's trust on mobile banking technology. Hence, having impression on adoption & acceptance of mobile based banking. Our findings against SYQ is also supported in earlier studies (Delone and McLean, 2003; Zhou, 2011; Peters et al., 2016; Upadhyay & Jahanyan, 2016; Shih & Fang, 2006; Shareef et al., 2014; Lee and Chung 2009; Faria, 2012; Arcand et al., 2017; Changchit et al., 2017).

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study and research work are restricted to only one province of Pakistan. To get more insights and information about the adoption of mobile based banking users, a study can be performed in other provinces of Pakistan. The study is focused on mobile application and system related factors and ignoring cultural differences among the people living in different cities and provinces. The acceptance of mobile banking might also be affected by cultural differences and behaviors (Constantiou et al., 2009). Similarly, the intention towards the technology, awareness, and beliefs are likely to differ and change with the time (Agarwal et al., 2000; Lee et al., 2003). Other variables like price value, habits, economic conditions, technology, and facilitation conditions can also be examined to understand the acceptance of mobile based banking.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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